

A LOOK AT SOCIETY IN SOCIOLOGY

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Abstract. This article will discuss the development of the direction of sociology, which is gaining popularity and development in our time, the views on it, the studies being conducted and their results. As the field of sociology develops, its consequences greatly affect society. While sociological research plays a huge role in the development of society, nowadays it has not gained popularity in our country.

Keywords: Sociology, social physics, O.Comte, T.Parsons, R.Merton, P.Lazersfeld, W.Ostwald, psychological views, macro sociology, microbiology.

ВЗГЛЯД НА ОБЩЕСТВО В СОЦИОЛОГИИ

Аннотация. В данной статье пойдет речь о развитии направления социологии, которое набирает популярность и развитие в наше время, взглядах на него, проводимых исследованиях и их результатах. По мере развития области социологии ее последствия сильно влияют на общество. Хотя социологические исследования играют огромную роль в развитии общества, в настоящее время они не приобрели популярности в нашей стране.

Ключевые слова: Социология, социальная физика, О.Конт, Т.Парсонс, Р.Мертон, П.Лазерсфельд, В.Оствальд, психологические взгляды, макросоциология, микробиология.

INTRODUCTION

Today, the field of sociology, which has developed and entered all the world countries, is also developing rapidly in our country. It is taught in depth in many universities. Social research centres are being opened to develop this field, and mature personnel of their work are growing every year.

The science of society as a whole system and of certain social orders, processes, social groups, and relations between individuals and society. Sociology can draw general conclusions based on empirical (experience-based) data generated using scientific methods. Because of this, it provides a scientific basis for the development models of the society.

Attempts to explain the life of society appeared in antiquity and continued in the philosophy of history. Important ideas about society, its existence and development are expressed in the works of Central Asian thinkers. Sociological ideas and views rose to the level of science in the first half of the 19th century as a result of the work of scientists such as O. Comte and G. Spencer, and have been developing for almost 200 years. The founder of sociology, the French thinker Auguste Comte, considers sociology to be a science based on the experience of society. In different periods, the essence of sociology was interpreted differently.

At first, it was understood as a general science of society. At the same time, it was also interpreted as social physics, referring to its specific scientific methods. Until the 19th century, sociology was a component of philosophy.

Sociology, which initially developed in Europe, began to present broad social problems in Western European countries with evidence and justification. In this sense, it was essentially macrosociology.

The development of sociology in America showed new aspects in the form of micro-sociology, which usually studies "small" social phenomena. Later, these macro and micro views of sociology were unified in the theoretical works of T. Parsons (1902-1979), R. Merton (1910) and P. Lazarsfeld (1901-1976) in the methodology of empirical research. However, debates about the subject of sociology and its importance for social practice are still ongoing, and attempts to create a new sociology have not yet stopped.

Sociology developed as a comprehensive system of knowledge in the classical period of its development, and then different currents and directions began to enter this science. Proponents of the mechanistic theory, G. Ch. Carey (1798-1879), V. Ostwald (1853-1932), and V. Pareto (1848-1923), considered sociology to be the physics of the social world. Biological theory, in particular, the organic direction (G. Spencer, L. Gumplovich), as well as representatives of social Darwinism (Ch. Darwin, etc.) interpreted society based on the laws of the biological world. In psychological views (D.S. Mill (1806-1873), Mac Dougall) events and processes in the life of society are explained psychologically based on the theory of analysis and the theory of instinct. In particular, Z. Freud (sexual orientation), Ya. Moreno's views (individual-psychological explanation of society) later led to collective-psychological theories. In this direction, social-psychological, behaviourist, symbolic interactionism, theories of social movements have developed.

Currently, functionalism is one of the main directions of modern Western sociology.

Representatives of this direction (T.Parsons, R.Merton) focus on the problems of functional unity of society, and its dynamic balance. The formal-sociological direction was strengthened and developed under the influence of sociologists such as F.Tennis (1855-1936), G.Zimmel, and L.Von Wiese (1876-1969). Representatives of this direction believe that it is more appropriate for the subject of sociology if more attention is paid to the form of social phenomena than to their content.

Sociology also has its history in Uzbekistan. It was expressed in the research of scholars, poets, thinkers and rulers who have been thinking about the problems of social existence for centuries. Our great compatriots made a great contribution to the development of sociology as well as other fields. Even though the idea of a perfect society, state management, and the place and role of an individual in society were the subject of works of various genres created by them, the opportunity to develop the science of sociology properly arose only after independence. In Uzbekistan, the skills of posing wide-scale theoretical and methodological problems and looking at the social world with an analytical eye are being formed.

Creating books and pamphlets, textbooks and manuals on sociology is becoming a vital need. Efforts are being made to form sociological thinking, to use it more widely in the education system, management, mass media and other areas. The Department of "Sociology and Management Psychology" operates at the State and Society Building Academy under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. For several years, the "Social Opinion" public opinion research center has accumulated experience in conducting sociological surveys.

Theoretical and practical research is being carried out in several scientific institutions (National University of Uzbekistan, Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan, regional universities). Even private research centres are operating in almost all regions of our country. This is another clear example of the development of the field of sociology in our country.

CONCLUSION

Sociology is a scientific and practical science that studies society and the social interaction of people. Sociological research ranges from the analysis of brief interactions between strangers on the street to the study of global social processes. Many areas of the discipline focus on how and why people are organized in society, as members of groups and institutions. As an academic discipline, sociology is generally considered a social science. Sociology is a set of disciplines that strive to explain the dimensions of society and the dynamics of society. Some of these disciplines, which reflect current areas of sociology, include demography, which studies changes in the size or type of population; studies criminology, criminal behaviour and diversion; social stratification, which examines inequality and class structure; political sociology, which studies government and law; sociology of race and sociology of gender, studies the social construction of race and gender, and race and gender inequality. New sociological fields and fields continue to develop, such as network analysis and environmental sociology; most of them are very disciplined by nature.

Sociology as a scientific discipline emerged in the early 19th century as an academic response to the problem of modernity: As the world becomes smaller and more integrated, people's experiences of the world are becoming more and more diffuse. Sociologists hoped not only to understand what held social groups together but also to develop a "medicine" against social fragmentation and exploitation. The term "sociology" was introduced by O. Comte in 1838 from the Latin word socio (companion, partner) and Greek logia (study, speech). Comte hoped to unify all human studies, including history, psychology, and economics. His sociological scheme was characteristic of the 19th century; he believed that all human life passed through the same historical stages and that if he understood this progress he could prescribe remedies for social ills.

The "classic" theorists of sociology of the late 19th and early 20th centuries include Ferdinand Tönnies, Emile Durkheim, Vilfredo Pareto, Ludwig Gumplowich, and Max Weber. Like Comte, these figures did not consider themselves "sociologists". Their works are devoted to religion, education, economics, law, psychology, ethics, philosophy and theology, and their theories have been applied in various scientific disciplines. Their influence on sociology was fundamental. The first books with the term "sociology" in the title were *Treatise on Sociology, Theoretical and Practical*, by North American lawyer Henry Hughes, and *The Sociology of the South, or the Failure of Free Society*, by North American lawyer George Fitzhugh. Both books were published in 1854 as part of the debate over slavery in the antebellum United States. The study of sociology appeared in 1874 by the English philosopher Herbert Spencer. Lester Frank Ward has been described by some as the father of American sociology.

In Europe between the wars, sociology was generally attacked by increasingly totalitarian governments and rejected by conservative universities. At the same time, first in Austria, and later in the USA, Alfred Schütz developed social phenomenology (which later informed social constructionism).

Also, members of the Frankfurt School (some of whom immigrated to the United States to escape Nazi persecution) developed critical theory by combining the critical, idealist, and historical materialist elements of the dialectical philosophy of Hegel and Marx with the concepts of Freud and Max Weber theory, if not always in the name) etc. In the 1930s in the USA, Talcott Parsons developed a structural-functional theory that combined the study of the "objective" aspects of social order and macro- and micro-structural factors. Since World War II, sociology has been revived in Europe, although under Stalin and Mao, it was suppressed in communist countries. In the mid-twentieth century, there was a general tendency for American sociology to become more scientific, partly due to the strong influence of structural functionalism at the time.

Sociologists have developed new types of quantitative research and qualitative research methods. In the second half of the twentieth century, sociological research was increasingly used as a tool by governments and businesses. Along with the emergence of various social movements in the 1960s, more attention was paid to theories emphasizing social struggle, including conflict theory (which attempted to counter structural functionalism) and neo-Marxist theories. Conflict theory dates back to thinkers such as Thomas Hobbes, but they are usually seen as part of Marxist thought. According to conflict theorists, individual groups within families, organizations, or societies are constantly fighting each other for control of resources.

This theory assumes that there is competition and inequality in society and that people who are aware of these facts will fight for their lives. Dramatic as it sounds, conflicts related to conflict theory can range from children vying for their parent's attention to countries fighting over land rights. This theory has great flexibility in the type of conflicts to which it applies.

Sociology is still a relatively young science compared to other social sciences, but it has found its place in scientific circles. Like other social sciences, sociology is becoming increasingly fragmented, specializing in topics that practitioners do not understand. The era of great theorists such as Comte, Marx, Weber, and Durkheim may have passed, but the field is alive with diversity. Sociologists use their tools to study anything and everything. There are minor disciplines for traditional fields such as economic and political sociology, but many sociologists study areas such as gender relations, social psychology, religion, health, and more. The above-mentioned industries are currently developing in Uzbekistan.

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